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Traditional research methods such as interviews or focus groups can be inadequate in the study of discrimination, especially with young people: results may be adversely affected by power hierarchies between researchers and research participants, but also by the fact that people are often uncomfortable and unwilling to talk about discriminatory experiences. Lack of full language proficiency in each other’s language by the researcher and research participants further adds to the complexity. To overcome these issues, we applied approaches deriving from the design research discipline that focuses on people’s direct experiences, placing them at the centre of the research activity and acknowledging their direct expertise on the subject.

BEYOND THE WORD: USING VISUAL TOOLS TO SUPPORT RESEARCH

In order to overcome the limitations posed by more traditional research methods, we adapted them in a designerly way, to generate new understandings of the topic and to communicate in both a more appealing and a more accessible way (Cross, 2006). Furthermore, a design approach is focused on tacit knowledge, which is generally difficult to articulate in spoken language but essential in diving deeper into people’s lived experiences. In our research, we drew inspiration from the generative approach discussed by Sanders and Stappers (2012). They claim that the act of “making”, contrary to “saying”, allows for a better expression of participants’ feelings as they become more explicit and tangible. This is why we developed tools that required participants to engage in an activity physically and aimed at overcoming conventional methods of inquiry based solely on verbal exchange. The choice of visual tools, which embraced various abstract and symbolic elements, such as shapes, scribbles, words, and emotional expressions (see Figure 1), was inspired by the psychology of colours and shapes and their ability to evoke certain emotional experiences or guide behaviours in specific cultural contexts (Jonaskaite et al., 2020; Frutiger, 1989). At the same time, an association between abstract elements and emotional state is broadly interpretable, especially in contexts with participants of diverse backgrounds. Our research acknowledged this vastity of meanings, and our tools were purposefully designed to provoke a ‘deliberate confusion’ and leave space for the mutual interpretation of the probe by both the participants and the researchers (Gaver et al., 2004).

METHODOLOGY

When preparing the research activity, we were guided by the following contextual frameworks:

- First of all, our research took place within the institutional context of schools. Participants were invited by their teacher, who served as gatekeeper in our research project. This created a context of unequal power dynamics, which might have influenced apprentices' attitudes and understanding of the activity.
- Time constraints resulted in a relatively short workshop (1 hour), as the apprentices we worked with only attend school once a week, and our research was held during the hours of another class. This made it difficult to build a strong relationship between the researchers and the participants, which is generally necessary when researching sensitive issues such as discrimination.
- The age of the apprentices (appr. 16-20 years) and the relatively large size of the groups influenced our decision to focus primarily on a collective activity instead of an individual one. This avoided putting research participants into a "spotlight" and allowed them to relate and compare their experience with that of others.
- About two-thirds of the participants were of migrant descent, and some were not fluent in Italian, the language in which the workshops were conducted. Therefore, it was necessary to consider language proficiency and how participants could express their thoughts without the need to articulate them verbally, making the research experience accessible to everyone. The participatory research activity comprised of a workshop model composed of two parts: a shared collective inquiry in a larger group and an individual inquiry focused more on personal experiences and narratives.

Collective Inquiry

The collective session aimed to provoke discussions on wicked problems through ludic tasks. Each session started with an explanation of the tool and the "rules" of the game. The first activity evolved around the big sheet of paper placed in the centre of the classroom, which introduced various macro-areas related to the apprenticeship experience. In particular, the sections included the physical work environment, tasks/activities and responsibilities, work conditions, and relations with managers, colleagues and clients. After explaining the single areas/sections and their specificities, a deck of 86 "playing" cards was introduced, including a list of adjectives and several graphic elements, such as shapes, scribbles, and colours [see appendix 1]. Participants were invited to place cards that best represented their emotions related to a specific macro-area. The interaction was quite intuitive: most of the cards were placed in the respective areas in a matter of minutes. Immediately after, the discussion took place.

Individual Inquiry

The class was divided into smaller groups, as a more personal approach in this phase was necessary since apprentices had to evaluate their individual work experience. Everyone was given a sheet of paper with a printed timeline and a set of stickers [see appendix 2]. The timeline represented the overall period that participants engaged in the

apprenticeship in question, specifically focussing on the differences that characterised the beginning of their apprenticeship, today, and their expectations for the end of the apprenticeship. Stickers included pre-defined elements related to apprenticeship, such as working hours, salary, work-life balance, and established relationships with colleagues, clients, managers, or teachers. Trainees were invited to position these elements on a “positive-negative” scale, while the emojis were supposed to help them represent their emotional state at a specific period.

flessibile
/
flexibel

tanto
/
viel

poco
/
wenig

complicato
/
kompliziert

difficile
/
schwierig

facile
/
einfach

divertente
/
unterhaltsam

noioso
/
langweilig

rispettoso
/
respektvoll

irrispettoso
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respektlos

caotico
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ordinato
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aggressivo
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collaborativo
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stimolante
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anregend

banale
/
banal

interessante
/
interessant

frustrante
/
frustrierend

inflexibile
/
unflexibel

esigente
/
anspruchsvoll

INDIVIDUAL INQUIRY

/ working
sheet (A4)

INDIVIDUAL INQUIRY

/ emoji
stickers

INDIVIDUAL INQUIRY

/ topic
stickers

